

SpaceTeamSat1
Preliminary Design Document
Ground Station and Radio Communication
PRELIMINARY

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Review History

The Preliminary Design Review (PDR) consists of two parts: First, this document itself and second, a review meeting in which the topics are discussed in person. In the following table the invited reviewers are listed. Additionally, it is stated if feedback to the document was received (DOC) as well as if the person participated in the PDR meeting (PDR).

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Contribution	Reviewer	Email	Justification
TBD	Lars Mehnen	lars.mehnen@technikum-wien.at	SSETI Express/RF specialist

Authors

Contribution	Name	Email
RF Communication	Jakob Riepler	jakob.riepler@spaceteam.at
Requirements	David Wagner	david.wagner@spaceteam.at

Contents

Abbreviations and Acronyms	viii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Related Documents	1
2 Requirements	2
3 Overview	4
3.1 Architecture	4
3.1.1 TX path	4
3.1.2 RX path	4
4 Communication Setup	7
4.1 SatNogs	7
4.2 Primary Ground Station	7
4.2.1 Mechanical Design	7
4.2.2 Electrical Design	8
4.2.3 Satellite tracking/uplink window	8
5 Mission Control	9
5.1 COSMOS	9
5.1.1 TX commands	9
5.1.2 RX telemetry packages	9
5.1.3 Large file transfer	9
5.2 Database	10
5.2.1 Large file management	10
5.3 SatNogs database	10
5.3.1 Grafana	10
5.4 Hardware	10
5.4.1 Remote setup	10
6 Protocol	11
6.1 Modulation	11
6.2 Synchronization and Channel Coding	11
6.3 Link Layer	12
6.3.1 Security and authentication	12
6.3.2 Packetization	12
6.4 Application Layer	12
6.4.1 ECSS services	12
6.5 Link Budget	13
7 RF communication test results	14
7.1 Mountain Field Test	14
7.2 High Altitude Flight	14

Contents

8 Discussion	15
Bibliography	16

Abbreviations and Acronyms

COBC	communication and on-board computer	9
FSK	frequency-shift keying	11
GFSK	gaussian frequency-shift keying	11, 13
GS	ground station	1–11, 15
HMAC	Hash-based Message Authentication Code	12
LHCP	Left Hand Circularly Polarized	4, 8
STS1	SpaceTeamSat 1	1, 2, 4, 8, 10, 15
TLE	Two-Line-Element	8, 15
TUST	TU Wien Space Team	10

1 Introduction

This document lays out the preliminary design for the ground station (GS) of the SpaceTeamSat 1 (STS1). In chapter 2, the requirements for successful operation of the STS1 concerning the GS will be listed. The architecture of the GS consists of two major parts, firstly the rotatable antenna and all additional components directly related to RF communications, and secondly, all software related to data management and the communication protocol. A more detailed overview of the whole architecture is given in chapter 3.

The GS operated by us (which shall be called primary GS) featuring a rotatable antenna will be responsible for sending commands and files to the CubeSat. It will also receive telemetry data and files from the CubeSat, though we will also utilize the SatNogs network to receive the regularly sent telemetry beacon packages, and possibly even extend our data downlink capacity. The details regarding the primary GS will be discussed in chapter 4.

In chapter 5, details of our data management as well as the system responsible for encoding and decoding of the application layer of our protocol will be stated. For the latter, we will use the COSMOS/OpenC3 GUI, which will enable us to operate on a completely decoded data level. The data of all packages sent and received will be fed into a SQLite database. Furthermore, the communication protocol used for TX and RX packages will be specified in chapter 6.

1.1 Related Documents

This table gives documents which build the base of the CubeSat architecture established so far.

Short Sign	Document Name	Purpose
STS1PDD[1]	CubeSat SpaceTeamSat1: Preliminary Design Document: System Architecture	Mission definition and design of the CubeSat system architecture
STS1DATA[2]	CubeSat SpaceTeamSat1: Dataflow Game	Design of the dataflow from the GS to the CubeSat and within the CubeSat

2 Requirements

In the following section, the requirements for the GS are described. All requirements are deduced from the STS1 System Architecture requirements [1]

The following subsystem requirement is deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement 7.2 [1]: The GS shall be able to send commands and data to the CubeSat.

- 7.2.GS.1 The GS shall be able to have all the defined commands used in the STS1 mission pre-defined. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.1
- 7.2.GS.2 The GS shall be able to automatically create a data packet that can be identified as a command by the CubeSat. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.1 and Section 5.1.1
- 7.2.GS.3 The GS shall be able to transmit RF packets such that the CubeSat can receive them. **Fulfilled:** In Section 4.2

The following subsystem requirement is deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement 7.3 [1]: The GS shall be able to download data from the CubeSat and store it locally within the GS infrastructure.

- 7.3.GS.1 The GS shall be able to receive RF packets sent by the CubeSat. **Fulfilled:** In Section 4.2
- 7.3.GS.2 The GS shall be able to automatically decode the received RF packets such that the data sent by the Cubesat can be stored. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.1 and Section 5.1.2
- 7.3.GS.3 The GS shall be able to store the data it receives from the Cubesat. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.2

The following subsystem requirement is deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement 7.4 [1]: The GS shall be able to run for at least seven days.

- 7.4.GS.1 The GS shall be able to run continuously. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.4

The following subsystem requirement is deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement 7.5 [1]: STS1 shall be able to download the entire generated data of one student code at least once every 48 hours. **Note:** The entire generated data is equivalent to the maximum data one student code generates during its whole run time, this is equivalent to the memory size in which the student code stores its data. This restricts the maximum amount of data and the number of photos a student code can produce, which is 1 MiB.

- 7.5.GS.1 The GS shall be able to receive, decode and store at least 1 MiB of student code generated data every 48 hours. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.4 and Section 6.1
- 7.5.GS.2 The GS shall continuously have enough storage to save 1 MiB every 48 hours. **Fulfilled:** In Section 5.4

The following subsystem requirement is deduced from STS1 System Architecture Requirement 7.6 [1]: All operations of the GS shall be configured to run manually or Autonomously. **Note:** “Autonomously” means that it does not require any human action.

2 Requirements

- 7.6.GS.1 The GS shall include a computer on which all the automation is calculated and managed.
Fulfilled: In Section [5.4](#)

3 Overview

This chapter gives an overview of the proposed GS architecture. The communication protocol for our communication is detailed in Chapter 6.

3.1 Architecture

The GS can be separated into three main parts.

The first part is our physical primary GS 4.2, which will have a Left Hand Circularly Polarized (LHCP) antenna on a mount that is able to rotate in both azimuth and elevation axis to actively track the CubeSat. It will be controlled by a Raspberry Pi running the SatNogs software stack which we will extend with transmit capabilities.

The second part is the SatNogs database and network 5.3, which will be used for scheduling observations, for publicly recording all received data, and for publishing a public dashboard featuring decoded telemetry data 5.3.1. Additionally, we will extend our downlink capacity by utilizing other receive-only GSs connected to the SatNogs network to receive beacons sent by the STS1, and possibly, also all other telemetry packages.

The last part is our software stack (based on COSMOS 5.1) that is responsible for providing us with an interface to encode and schedule commands for the CubeSat and decode any received data from the CubeSat. It also includes a database 5.2, which stores relevant data from all packages sent or received.

3.1.1 TX path

If a command shall be sent to the CubeSat, the first step is for an operator to use the GUI of COSMOS 5.1 to interactively create a command and schedule it for the next uplink window. The command will then be encoded by COSMOS into one or multiple packets which are queued for transmission. This queue is sorted by command priority to make sure that commands of high importance reach the CubeSat first. Once the uplink window starts, these packets will be transmitted to the primary GS where they are wrapped into a channel coding and forward error correction and converted into FSK modulated I/Q data which is then transmitted using an SDR transceiver. The process is illustrated in fig. 3.1.

3.1.2 RX path

Downlink packages can be received by either the primary ground station 4.2 or any other GS connected to the SatNogs network.

In the first case, the data gets sent directly to COSMOS 5.1 for processing using a TCP socket, and additionally it is archived in the SatNogs database 5.3 which does its own data decoding to provide the public telemetry dashboard.

3 Overview

Figure 3.1: Flowchart of the TX data path.

In the second case, the data is only stored in the SatNogs database (including the aforementioned processing for the public dashboard). We will create a crawler to regularly import data from other GSs on the SatNogs network into COSMOS for decoding.

In both cases, the data will be decoded by both the SatNogs network to display a public telemetry dashboard and COSMOS for processing the received data on our side. COSMOS then provides us with all data sent by the CubeSat. This data will be fed into our own SQLite database. The process is illustrated in fig. 3.2.

(a) If the signal is received by our primary ground-station.

(b) If the signal is received by any other SatNogs groundstation.

Figure 3.2: Flowcharts for the RX path

4 Communication Setup

4.1 SatNogs

[SatNogs](#) is a community project initiated by the Libre Space Foundation with the aim to build a free-to-use, open-source satellite GS network.

It is built for receive-only as allowing people to transmit on equipment of others - possibly in other countries - can be a legal issue but it is easy to extend with transmit capabilities only controllable by us.

They provide different suggestions for GS setup ranging from very easy to build to highly sophisticated which is ideal for our educational objective.

4.2 Primary Ground Station

Our primary GS is based on a rotatable design with a highly directional antenna. This is necessary to keep the margin in our link budget calculation as high as possible, as this gives us a high chance of success for data transfers and maybe even allowing us to increase data rates further to allow for larger data transfers.

4.2.1 Mechanical Design

Rotator

The rotator is the SatNogs v3.1 rotator design (https://wiki.satnogs.org/SatNOGS_Rotator_v3), as it is relatively cheap to build and is well integrated into the SatNogs software stack. We plan on switching to an alternative design called "SuperAntennaz" (<https://wiki.satnogs.org/SuperAntennaz>), as it provides better stability and lifetime while being slightly more expensive (but still well below comparable commercial rotors).

Mount and Mast

The mount is a commercial satellite dish mount for flat roofs. It is held down using eight concrete slabs thus requiring no permanent modifications to the roof.

Enclosure

The electronics are enclosed in an aluminium waterproof box usually used by wireless internet service providers for outdoor wifi equipment. It has enough room to house all required electronics except for the RF path.

Antenna and RF Electronics

The antenna is an 8-turn LHCP helical antenna based on the SatNogs v5 helical antenna design (<https://ohai.libre.space/project/helical-antenna-v5/>). The RF electronics are mounted directly behind the antenna in a waterproof enclosure to minimize cable losses by keeping all RF paths as short as possible.

4.2.2 Electrical Design

Power Supply

The GS is supplied with 230V. The main electronics enclosure contains a 48V power supply which is used for the rotor and a 5V supply which is used for everything else.

Compute and Network

The main computer used in the GS is a Raspberry Pi Model 4B as it is small, relatively cheap and has enough power to handle the signal processing. It is connected to the internet using an outdoor rated glass fiber connected to the Pi through a media converter. This minimizes the risk for any equipment damage indoors in case of a lightning strike.

RF

The Pi is connected to a HackRF One SDR, which is used for both receiving and transmitting. The RX path is connected from the antenna to an FM-broadcast filter (80-100MHz band stop filter), to an LNA (Nooelec LaNA) and to the SDR. The TX path is connected from the SDR to a band pass (420-440MHz), to an LNA (SPF5189, used as a pre-amplifier), to a 5W amplifier, to a low pass filter and to the antenna. Both paths are connected to the SDR and the antenna through an RX/TX switch which is controlled by a GPIO pin of the HackRF One.

4.2.3 Satellite tracking/uplink window

Observations of our satellite can be scheduled via SatNogs, which will provide the spatial information required for tracking STS1 during its pass. For this, SatNogs requires a regularly updated (as of now, we do not know what interval would be necessary for succesfull operation, our best guess would be once a week) Two-Line-Element (TLE), which it may acquire from several different sources, including <https://www.space-track.org>. It is not yet clear how we ensure that the TLE is tracked.

We define our uplink window to start once we receive a package from the cubesat, and end when the cubesat is out of the range of our primary GS.

5 Mission Control

5.1 COSMOS

We will use the COSMOS/OpenC3 software (<https://openc3.com/>) to handle both the creation of the bitstream of the application layer for TX commands and to interpret the application layer of RX telemetry packages. For that purpose, the application layer protocol defined in 6.4 will be fully implemented in the COSMOS syntax, including the definitions of all command and telemetry IDs. COSMOS provides a GUI with which commands can easily be created and sent, and telemetry packages can be viewed.

5.1.1 TX commands

A command can be sent by selecting the desired command in the COSMOS GUI and then filling out all the variable parameters of the command, by selecting a category and/or entering a base 10 number. COSMOS should then add a unique ID to the command and create the bitstream which will be forwarded to the primary GS.

5.1.2 RX telemetry packages

The bitstream of a telemetry package received by COSMOS will be interpreted and displayed in the GUI. COSMOS will also be able to assign text to certain ID variables, so data can be displayed in a comprehensible form. Furthermore, the relevant parts of the received data shall be extracted from COSMOS to be fed into our database 5.2.

5.1.3 Large file transfer

Large files will have to be separated into parts small enough to be sent as commands. To prepare files for transmission to the cubesat, we wrote a python script which reads the file and then creates a COSMOS command setup text file, which includes commands for each part of the separated file. Besides the bytes of the part of the file, each command will also include an ID uniquely identifying the part of the file, such that the communication and on-board computer (COBC) can correctly concatenate all parts. This solution is not ideal, as the COSMOS server has to be updated every time one wants to transmit a large file. During the update process, received packages will be deleted from the COSMOS server. Thus, it has to be ensured by the person handling the large file upload, that no data is lost during the progress.

Handling of receiving large files has not yet been discussed, though it should be significantly simpler than sending large files.

5.2 Database

We build a database using SQLite, with the database file stored locally on the primary GS PC section 5.4. A back up schedule will be necessary, but has not yet been thought through. The database shall store all relevant data of all packages sent and received. This includes the unique package ID, the time at which these packages were sent/received and, depending on the type of the package, all variable data fields of the package (e.g. reset counts, temperatures, ...). We shall use a python script which will read CSV files created by the COSMOS data extractor tool and then feed the information from these files into the database.

5.2.1 Large file management

While we can store the separate packages used for large file transfers in the SQLite database, it is not well suited to store the merged files. It is yet unclear how we can join the received packages together, store them and make them publicly available.

5.3 SatNogs database

The global network of SatNogs GSs (<https://network.satnogs.org/>) will be used to receive telemetry packages from GSs all over the world, thus greatly increasing the time in which signals may be received. We shall provide the SatNogs database with all the necessary information to decode (at least) the beacons of the STS1. These include a flowgraph, a Kaitai decoder and all information about our transmitter. The data will then be available in the SatNogs database for further usage. We will implement tooling to import data from the SatNogs database into COSMOS to make data transfers quicker and more reliable, especially with large file transfer in mind.

5.3.1 Grafana

We will use a Grafana dashboard to visualize data we receive from Beacons. The dashboard will receive the data directly from the SatNogs database. Data can be displayed in time-dependent graphs or as plain text interpretations of booleans, among other ways. Also includes the possibility of color-coding parameter ranges. The dashboard will be publicly available on <https://dashboard.satnogs.org/>, realizing maximal readability of our data for both the team and interested third-parties.

5.4 Hardware

The hardware for Mission Control will be a PC at the TU Wien Space Team (TUST) headquarter. On this PC we will run COSMOS 5.1 and our database 5.2. This PC has to run continuously to ensure that no telemetry packages will be missed. Furthermore, enough storage to store more than 1MiB of data every 48 hours is required. Additionally, a backup strategy for the received data is desirable, but has not yet been developed.

5.4.1 Remote setup

No plans have yet been made on how to operate the primary GS remotely.

6 Protocol

6.1 Modulation

For data communication, the GS will use frequency-shift keying (FSK) or gaussian frequency-shift keying (GFSK) modulation. The baud rate is variable from 1200 to 115200 baud. During commissioning after launch, the baud rate is set to 1200 with our target being at least 9600 baud during regular operation. Baud rate selection is separate for up- and downlink and will reset to the lowest supported rate after a specified time of no successful two-way communication.

In more intuitive units this equals 9 kB per minute of visibility in the worst case (1200 baud), 72 kB with our lowest target baud rate (9600 baud) and 864 kB per minute at the highest supported baud rate (115200 baud). It is important to note, that these numbers do not include any protocol overhead, which could be more than 40%. A pass of the satellite in range of a GS usually takes in the order of five to ten minutes, with more than one pass per day to be expected, though we do not have detailed information on this topic yet.

Additionally, morse code will be used to regularly transmit the CubeSat's callsign, as it is easily decodeable by ear and has a very low SNR requirement for successful reception.

6.2 Synchronization and Channel Coding

Synchronization and channel coding will be based on the CCSDS standards 131.0-B-4 [3] and 231.0-B-4 [4]. The upstream direction might feature a slight deviation from said standards and use Reed-Solomon encoding also for telecommand (uplink). This allows us to reduce code complexity by using the same encoding for up- and downlink.

SatNogs currently only supports a limited set of coding schemas. We will most likely use the following parameters for telemetry (downlink):

- Punctured convolutional code with puncture pattern 11 (CCSDS 131.0 3.4 [3]), which results in a code rate of 2/3.
- Reed-Solomon 255,223 decoding
- CCSDS 131.0 10.4 [3] descrambler with 0xFF initialization value
- 8x 0x33 preamble detection
- sync word ([0x3C, 0x67, 0x49, 0x52]) detection and sync
- CRC32_C checksum checking

And the following parameters for telecommand (uplink):

- CRC32_C checksum generation
- Reed-Solomon 255,223 encoding (nonstandard for uplink)
- Data pseudorandomization (231.0 6.2)

- prepend [0x3C, 0x67, 0x49, 0x52] sync word
- prepend 8x 0x33 preamble

Possible changes include but are not limited to switching to low density parity codes instead of Reed-Solomon encoding should the lower overhead for larger packet sizes outweigh the way higher minimum packet size.

6.3 Link Layer

The link layer will use the CCSDS Space Data Link Protocol as defined in CCSDS 132.0-B-3 [5] and CCSDS 232.0-B-4 [6]. It allows us to merge multiple data streams into a single physical channel.

6.3.1 Security and authentication

Telecommand data will be signed by us to prevent unauthorized data uplink by third parties ("hijacking"). This authorization will be based on the CCSDS Space Data Link Security Protocol (CCSDS 355.0-B-2 [7]). It provides replay protection using sequence numbers, cryptographic signatures and optional encryption. The applicable cryptographic algorithms are listed in CCSDS 352.0-B-2 [8].

We will use a symmetric Hash-based Message Authentication Code (HMAC) cipher as it is faster and we would not profit from using asymmetric cryptography in this usecase. The minimal-size HMAC standardized by CCSDS is HMAC-SHA224 which has a length of 224 bit. Should we want to further reduce the overhead of the authentication, we can alternatively implement HMAC with truncated Blake2s with at least 64 bit. While being nonstandard it would provide us with enough security and less processing time requirement on the CubeSat.

6.3.2 Packetization

The space data link layer protocol creates data streams which are segmented into packets by the space packet protocol (CCSDS 133.0-B-2 [9]).

6.4 Application Layer

We decided to base our application layer protocol on the ECSS standard ECSS-E-ST-70-41C [10] which defines many different service types of which we only need a small subset.

6.4.1 ECSS services

At least the following services and command subsets will be implemented by us:
ST[01] request verification:

- TM[1,1] successful acceptance verification report
- TM[1,2] failed acceptance verification report

ST[03] housekeeping:

- TM[3,25] housekeeping parameter report
- ??

ST[08] function management:

- TC[8,1] perform a function
- ??

ST[20] parameter management:

- TC[20,1] report parameter values
- TM[20,2] parameter value report
- TC[20,3] set parameter values

Additional standard service types might get implemented for file transfers, historic housekeeping data download, min/max/avg statistics reporting and event reporting. Should functionality not be covered by this standard in a way that fits our requirements, it will be implemented using custom service types.

6.5 Link Budget

Link budget was calculated using the AMSAT-IARU link model spreadsheet [11]. The calculation was done with the preliminary selection of channel coding and error correction parameters listed above and GFSK modulation.

The telecommand link margin is:

- 23.6dB at 1200 baud
- 14.6dB at 9600 baud
- 3.8dB at 115200 baud

The telemetry link margin is:

- 21.8dB at 1200 baud
- 12.8dB at 9600 baud
- 2.0dB at 115200 baud

7 RF communication test results

7.1 Mountain Field Test

The field test spanned a distance of 30 km with a clear line of sight from Hohe Wand to Müllendorf. It included the full but not yet perfectly tuned RF path of the Cube Sat with the final antenna design and the non-rotating ground station (QFH Antenna and RTL-SDR) without an LNA, as we were saturating the receiver when using an LNA (Nooelec LANA). While only the morse code was decoded on the spot, the signal strength was way more than required for FSK demodulation. IQ recordings were made during the field day, enabling us to decode the FSK data after the fact for validation of our FSK transmission code on the CubeSat. Only the transmitter of the Cube Sat was tested. Receiving data on the Cube Sat was not tested.

7.2 High Altitude Flight

Currently, the high altitude flight is scheduled after the PDR of this document.

8 Discussion

- The TLE of STS1 will only be available after approximately two days. After that, it will be provided by the NORAD, for which we do not have to act in any way. Before that, especially on the first pass (roughly 90min after deployment), we shall use a handheld antenna, with which we manually track the satellite.
- The complete protocol/process for sending commands should be documented clearly and saved, such that we can still communicate even if the mission lasts way longer than expected (and different people may be active on the project).
- Further thought should be put into the thunderstorm protection of our primary GS, we suggest a relay 0.35db loss directly after the antenna. Alternatively, a person responsible for the primary GS, who turns it off when there is any danger, was suggested.
- For the replay protection part of the authentication for our TX commands, we should have the option to reset the sequence number. Otherwise, we may not be able to send any commands after some irregularities.
- We need to track the current state of the software of the satellite, such that it is understandable and manageable also when the person mainly responsible for it is not available.

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